

Postoperative Results in Patients Undergoing Treatment of Fractures of the Lateral End Clavicle by Hook Plate

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Abstract:

Background: Fracture lateral ends of clavicle were vulnerable for instability and remain a challenge for the orthopedic surgeons. The clinical result of fracture fixation of lateral end clavicle using hook plate was described and practiced by any surgeons and seemed to be well accepted by others in terms of fracture union and function. The principal advantages were anatomical reduction of the fracture and early rehabilitation which lead to good shoulder girdle function.

Aim of the Study: The aim of this study is to evaluate the functional outcomes of clavicle hook plate fixation for fractures of the lateral clavicle and acromio-clavicular joint disruption; to evaluate the outcomes of managing unstable fractures of the lateral end of the clavicle using a clavicle hook plate.

Materials: This study included 31 patients with displaced fractures of the lateral end of the clavicle, all treated with clavicle hook plate fixation. The mean age of the patients was 29.55±3.5 years, with a range from 18 to 55 years.

Results: The mean follow-up period was 18 months, with a range of 12 to 20 months. The average fracture healing time was 10.25±1.35 weeks post-operatively. One patient (03.22%) experienced nonunion but had good alignment and remained asymptomatic without functional disability. Another patient (03.22%) developed a superficial wound infection, while a third (03.22%) had impingement, which resolved after plate removal. Additionally, one patient (03.22%) developed acromio-clavicular (AC) joint arthrosis. The mean Constant score for the affected shoulder was 87.95±2.50 points (range, 85–100), while the score for the contralateral shoulder averaged 92.65±20 points (range, 92–100). Plate removal was performed in only three patients-(09.67%).

Conclusion: The clavicle hook plate is an effective method for managing lateral end clavicle fractures, providing stable fixation with a low complication rate. Plate removal is not necessary in most cases.

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Introduction

Displaced fractures of the lateral third of the clavicle are less common than fractures of the middle third, accounting for approximately 15% of all clavicle fractures. [1] Only one-third of these fractures is displaced (Neer type II) and is associated with a higher rate of delayed union or nonunion. Surgical treatment of these fractures presents challenges due to the small bone fragment, proximity to the acromio-clavicular (AC) joint and soft metaphyseal bone in this region. [2] Various surgical methods have been proposed for treating these fractures; including Kirschner wire fixation, coraco-clavicular screw fixation, plate fixation, and

arthroscopic techniques. [3] However, none of these approaches is universally accepted as the gold standard treatment. [4] The hook plate system allows for early rotational mobility of the shoulder and has shown favorable outcomes in several studies. However, it has also been associated with complications such as nonunion, infection, and acromial osteolysis. [5] Fractures of the lateral end of the clavicle represent approximately 15% of all clavicle fractures, while 9% of shoulder girdle injuries involve damage to the acromio-clavicular (AC) joint. [6] These fractures often lead to disruption of the coraco-clavicular ligaments and

are considered unstable due to four main displacing forces that hinder healing. [7] The nonunion rate for these fractures is around 30%, which results in pain and impaired function of the shoulder girdle and upper limb. [8] As a result, surgical intervention is typically recommended for unstable distal clavicle fractures. [9] Over the years, various surgical treatments have been developed, each with varying degrees of success. [10] Currently, the clavicle hook plate is widely accepted as a viable surgical option for these injuries. [11] The present study was conducted with two objectives: first, to analyze the outcomes of clavicle hook plate fixation in comparison with existing literature, and second, to assess the need for repair of the soft tissue structures surrounding the acromio-clavicular joint. The evaluation will be based on clinical outcomes and radiological assessments to determine the efficacy of this procedure. The aim of this study is to evaluate the functional outcomes of clavicle hook plate fixation for fractures of the lateral clavicle and acromio-clavicular joint disruption.

Materials

The objective of this study was to assess the outcomes of using AO hook plates for treating Neer type II distal clavicle fractures. A secondary aim was to determine whether clavicle plates should be removed after fracture union. An ethics committee clearance was obtained before commencing the study. An ethics committee approved consent form and proforma was used to collect the data. 31 patients with radiological evidence and clinical evidence of unstable lateral fragment of clavicle fracture were included in the study. The study period was between February 2021 and December 2024.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients aged between 18 and 55 years were included. Patients of both the genders were included. Patients with NEER Type II fractures of the clavicle were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients aged below 18 years and above 55 years were excluded. Patients with Diabetes Mellitus, immune-compromised diseases were excluded. Patients with osteoporosis were excluded. Patients with skin lesions around the fracture site were excluded. All the patients were thoroughly examined clinically and radiologically. Patients were graded as per Neer classification of clavicle fractures.

Surgical Technique: The surgery was performed in a beach-chair position under general anesthesia. A standard Thompson incision, 6 to 8 cm in length, was made, centered over the fracture site. The fracture site was exposed, and the interposed soft tissue was removed. After reducing the fracture, a hook plate was used to fix it in place. The torn coraco-clavicular ligament was left unrepaired. The

hook of the plate was passed under the acromion, and the shaft of the plate was positioned on the superior cortex of the clavicle, held in place by bone reduction forceps.

Fluoroscopy was used to confirm the position of the plate and the motion of the shoulder before definitive fixation. The clavicle hook plate was then fixed to the medial fragment of the clavicle using 3.5-mm cortical screws, and the wound was closed. During the first three weeks post-surgery, the arm was held in a sling. Passive movements were allowed, but overhead abduction was prohibited. After three weeks, patients were encouraged to perform active movements. Radiographs were taken every three weeks, and the Constant score was used to evaluate shoulder function.

Statistical Analysis: Mean, standard deviation (\pm SD), Minimum and maximum values (range) for numerical data and Frequency and percentage for non-numerical data.

Analytical-Statistics:

1. One-way ANOVA: To assess the statistical significance of differences between the means of more than two groups.

2. Independent-samples t-test: Used to assess the statistical significance of differences between the means of the two study groups.

3. Pearson correlations: Used to assess the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables (correlation coefficient, r).

4. Chi-square test and Fisher's exact test: Used to compare qualitative data between different groups. P-value: Level of significance: $P \leq 0.05$: Significant (S); $P \leq 0.01$: Highly significant (HS)

Results

Clavicle hook plate fixation was performed on 31 patients among them 19 (61.29%) were males and 12 (38.70%) were females with displaced fractures of the lateral end of the clavicle between. The mean age of the patients was 29.55 ± 3.5 years, with a range from 18 to 55 years. 18 (58.06%) patients had fractures on the right side, and 13 (41.93%) had fractures on the left side. All the fractures were in accordance with the Neer type II fracture features. 10 (32.25%) patients were heavy manual laborers. 11 (35.48%) were doing white collar jobs and 05 (16.12%) were unemployed youth; the remaining 05 (35.48%) were college students. All the patients were subjected to the same technique of clavicle hook plate fixation under General anesthesia. There was no statistical significant difference in the demographic data of the subjects in the study (p -value more than 0.05).

Table 1: Showing the Demographic data of the study subjects (n-31)

Observation	Number	Percentage	P value
Age			
18 to 27 years	08	25.80	0.114
28 to 37 years	10	32.25	
38 to 47 years	07	22.58	
48 to 55 Years	06	19.35	
Mean Age	26.55±4.5	32.75±1.5	
Gender			
Male	19	61.29	0.310
Female	12	38.70	
Employment			
Hard Laborer	10	35.48	0.152
White collar job	11	32.25	
Unemployed	05	16.12	
Student	05	16.12	
Side of involvement			
Right	18	58.06	0.166
Left	13	41.93	

The mean follow-up period was 18 months, with a range of 12 to 20 months. The mean fracture healing time was 10.25±1.35 weeks post-operatively in the males and 12.15±0.95 weeks in the females. One patient (03.22%) experienced nonunion in the males and 02 (06.45%) patients in the female group but had good alignment and remained asymptomatic without functional disability.

Another patient (03.22%) developed a superficial wound infection among the males and 02 (%) patients among the females. 01 (03.22%) patient developed impingement among the males and none in the females. The impinged fracture site resolved after plate removal in the male. Additionally, one patient (03.22%) in both the genders developed

acromio-clavicular (AC) joint arthrosis. The mean Constant score for the affected shoulder was 87.95±2.50 points (range, 85–100) in the males and 85.15±1.50 in the females, while the score for the contralateral shoulder averaged 92.65±20 points (range, 92–100) in the males and 90.55. ±3.10 points (range, 92–100) in the females.

The mean return time to duties was 02.10±0.55 months in the males and 02.30.50±1.55 months in the females after surgery. There were no intra-operative complications. No fractures of the acromion were encountered, and no acromial osteolysis was noted. The plate was removed in 06 (19.35%) patients in the males and 03 (09.67%) in the females. (Table 2)

Table 2:

Observation	Male	Female	P value
Mean fracture healing time	10.25±1.35	12.15±0.95	
Complications			
Non-Union	01- (03.22%)	02- (06.45%)	0.110
Superficial wound infection	02- (06.45%)	02- (06.45%)	
Impingement	01- (03.22%)	00- (0%)	
acromio-clavicular (AC) joint arthrosis	01- (03.22%)	01- (03.22%)	
The mean Constant score for the affected shoulder	87.95±2.50 points (range, 85–100)	85.15±1.50 points (range, 85–100)	0.001
Number of Plate removals	06- (19.35%)	03 (03.22%)	0.001
Mean return time to duties (months)	02.10±0.55	02.30.50±1.55	0.001

Discussion

Displaced fractures of the lateral third of the clavicle are far less common than fractures of the middle third and account for approximately 15% of all clavicle fractures. [12]

Minimally displaced clavicle fractures can usually be treated non-operatively, but surgical treatment is recommended for unstable fractures of the lateral

end of the clavicle (Neer type II) due to a higher risk of nonunion. [13] Neer suggested that the high rate of nonunion can be attributed to the deforming forces acting on the fracture site, which cause continuous motion at the fracture ends, leading to displacement. [14] Edwards et al. [15] treated 43 patients with type II fractures of the lateral clavicle using conservative methods. They found a high incidence of local complications, residual shoulder

dysfunction, and nonunion, recommending open reduction and internal fixation as the treatment of choice. Surgical treatment of this unstable fracture can be challenging because of the small, often comminuted bony fragment, the proximity of the fracture to the AC joint, and the soft metaphyseal bone in this area. Various methods have been suggested for treating these fractures, such as K-wire fixation, modified tension band fixation, and Bosworth-type screw fixation.

However, these methods have been associated with significant issues such as hardware failure and migration. Furthermore, plate fixation is not possible if the distal fragment cannot support two or more cortical screws. In this study clavicle hook plate fixation was performed on 31 patients among them 19 (61.29%) were males and 12 (38.70%) were females with displaced fractures of the lateral end of the clavicle between. The mean age of the patients was 29.55 ± 3.5 years, with a range from 18 to 55 years. 18 (58.06%) patients had fractures on the right side, and 13 (41.93%) had fractures on the left side.

All the fractures were in accordance with the Neer type II fracture features. 10 (32.25%) patients were heavy manual laborers. 11 (35.48%) were doing white collar jobs and 05 (16.12%) were unemployed youth; the remaining 05 (35.48%) were college students. It was hypothesized following this study that using a clavicle hook plate can address the difficulties in fixing the small lateral fragment, preserve mobility of the acromio-clavicular joint, and promote early recovery of shoulder function without the need for coracoclavicular ligament reconstruction.

In a comparative study, Lee et al. treated 52 patients with unstable distal clavicle fractures using either open reduction or internal fixation with hook plates or tension band wires. [16] They reported fewer complications in the hook plate group compared to the tension band wire group ($P=0.01$). In the hook plate group, there was one (03.1%) complication due to screw loosening and partial loss of reduction. In contrast, the tension band wire group had six (30%) complications, including one complete loss of reduction with nonunion, three partial losses of reduction, and two superficial infections.

K-wire migration is a significant concern, especially with osteoporotic bones. In studies using K-wires, 10–15% of patients experienced implant migration. Kona et al. [17] treated 13 patients with unstable lateral clavicle fractures using K-wires and reported 11 unsatisfactory results (six non-unions and five infections). They concluded that K-wire fixation should not be recommended for such fractures.

In the present study, the plate was removed in 06 (19.35%) patients, five of whom requested the removal despite the absence of symptoms. The present data are consistent with Faraj and Ketzer, [18] who used hook plates in ten patients with acromio-clavicular injuries (three fractures). All fractures united, and the patients had pain-free function, with no plate removals performed.

In this study, 29 (93.54%) patients were completely pain-free. Except for two patients (06.45%), all patients were able to return to work and previous athletic activities in a short time. The design of the hook plate provides stable fixation, and most researchers in the literature have reported good outcomes with few complications.

Our results align with theirs. [19] Although the hook plate could theoretically cause rotator cuff injury or sub-acromial impingement, we found that it did not produce impingement. This could be explained by the fact that the hook of the plate typically occupies the posterior part of the sub-acromial space, away from the site of impingement. Haidar et al. [20] reported that the plate does not affect the AC joint if it is placed correctly. The vertical part of the hook should pass behind the AC joint. Migration of the plate anteriorly could affect the joint, but this is nearly impossible if the plate is securely fixed to the shaft.

Conclusion

The clavicle hook plate is an effective method for fixing fractures of the lateral end of the clavicle. It provides stable fixation with a low complication rate, and removal of the plate is not necessary.

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